

GOOSE: Good Object-Oriented System Experience

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Abstract

We present GOOSE (Good Object-Oriented System Experience) – an object-oriented abstraction layer for the Anoma Resource Machine (Anoma RM) that lets developers write applications in terms of classes, objects, and methods while compiling to resource-based transactions and Resource Logics (RLs) that are correct by construction. GOOSE represents objects as RM resources and method calls as messages inducing actions. The RLs enforce class invariants and method logics, ensuring strong object interface safety: any valid transaction that modifies a GOOSE object, whether compiler-generated or hand-crafted, must correspond to a sequence of permitted interface calls. We demonstrate the expressiveness and usability of this approach with a Kudos Bank case study that supports minting, transfers, checks, and auctions.

Keywords: object-oriented programming ; Anoma ; Resource Machine ;

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1. Introduction

Anoma [GYB23] is a distributed operating system for intent-centric applications that unifies underlying blockchains into a single development environment, thereby mitigating the fragmentation of state and users that limits today’s decentralized applications. In the present paper, we show how this vision can be extended with an object-oriented interface.

Smart contracts are the default organization principle for operating with digital assets, sometimes simplified to the idea of programmable money. For a long time, smart contract state has been accessible to the general public. Arbitrary private state transitions were available only for limited operations, e.g., the transfer of assets in a shielded pool. Anoma has developed the Anoma Resource Machine [KG24] (ARM or Anoma RM) to enable arbitrary shielded state transitions. The ARM is the part of the Anoma protocol responsible for creating, composing, and verifying transactions which create and consume resources. In this respect, its role in the Anoma protocol is similar to the role of the Ethereum Virtual Machine in the Ethereum protocol.

At the level of the Anoma Resource Machine, any state is represented as immutable resources, and all state transitions are expressed as transactions that consume and create resources subject to a balance check and resource-specific logic functions. This design provides a principled foundation for security and local reasoning about state updates. Still, it also exposes application developers to an unfamiliar, complex interface that is difficult to use directly. Even for simple applications, writing ARM transactions by hand requires careful management of resource labels, kinds, nonces, quantities, and resource logics.

In contrast, mainstream application developers are accustomed to working in object-oriented programming (OOP) environments where state is encapsulated in objects and manipulated via methods. Such environments provide a natural way to factor application code into classes, objects, and method calls,

and they support reasoning in terms of domain concepts rather than underlying execution machinery. The Anoma Virtual Machine (AVM) [Hei25] proposes such an object-centric view for Anoma. However, the AVM defines an object-oriented model on a very abstract level, without specifying the details of its representation in the ARM. Bridging the gap between an OOP-style surface language and the ARM in a way that ensures security and composability is non-trivial.

GOOSE (Good Object-Oriented System Experience) is our answer to this problem. GOOSE provides an object-oriented programming layer on top of the ARM. Developers write applications in a familiar style using classes, fields, constructors, and methods, and GOOSE compiles them into correct-by-construction ARM transactions and resource logics. Conceptually, each object is represented by an RM resource, each method or constructor call translates to a sent message, and each message induces an RM action (a component of a transaction) together with the corresponding resource logics (RLs) that enforce the intended behaviour. With GOOSE, developers focus on domain-level behaviour, while the translation handles generating transactions and resource logics. The application developer does not need to know anything about the ARM.

An important property of the GOOSE translation is that it guarantees *object interface security*. In other words, objects can only be modified in accordance with their public interface, and this is ensured also at the ARM level. Even if a malicious actor tries to submit a transaction directly, bypassing the GOOSE layer, they still cannot modify GOOSE objects (more precisely – their corresponding resources) in a way not allowed by the object interface. The only operations possible on an object are the ones defined by its methods.

The GOOSE translation is compositional. Each method call is independently compiled to a separate action (a subdivision of an ARM transaction). These actions are composed into a single transaction that represents the translation of a GOOSE program. The generated RLs ensure that any transaction involving an object resource conforms to the object’s interface, i.e., that it implements one of the object’s methods.

GOOSE programs that constitute object method bodies translate to both transactions and resource logics. The method code determines the updated object resource in a transaction for a method call. It also determines the constraints in the RL, which ensure the transaction’s conformance to the object interface. The GOOSE approach may therefore require compiling the same object-oriented code to two or more fundamentally different targets, because Anoma transactions and resource logics may be represented in two unrelated programming systems, e.g., Elixir for transaction submission and a zkVM for resource logics.

In this report, we present GOOSE programs in an object-oriented pseudocode, but GOOSE by itself is not a programming language. Rather, GOOSE provides a specification of an object-oriented framework and its translation to the Anoma Resource Machine. The GOOSE framework may be implemented in any programming language which is expressive enough to represent GOOSE concepts. In the appendix, we discuss an implementation of GOOSE in Lean 4.

2. Motivation

Building Anoma applications [HR24] directly on the Anoma Resource Machine (ARM) [KG24] exposes developers to a low-level interface designed for precise control and safety of state updates. In practice, authoring applications directly on the ARM requires juggling many interconnected concepts: resources and their invariants (moderated by the resource logic functions), nonces, actions, delta proofs, compliance units, transactions, etc. – each of which is necessary for correctness, but collectively they create a high barrier to entry and slow down iteration.

GOOSE (Good Object-Oriented System Experience) addresses this by providing an object-oriented programming layer on top of the ARM. The core idea is simple: developers write in a familiar OOP style – classes, fields, constructors, methods – and GOOSE compiles those programs to correct-by-construction ARM transactions and resource logic functions. With GOOSE, programmers concentrate on application domain behaviour; the compiler takes on the mechanical and security-critical details that the ARM demands (e.g., nonce management, well-balanced transactions, generating resource logic functions that ensure objects can only be modified only through their public interface).

2.1. Why not program in the ARM directly?

The ARM provides a low-level programming model unfamiliar to mainstream application developers, who would be better served with established object-oriented concepts.

At the ARM level, an “object” is a resource carrying state and quantity, and correctness is enforced by both the resource logic and the balance checks: logic functions guard every admissible state transition and balance checks ensure that each transaction is balanced. Defining a new object and establishing its behaviour involves:

- Designing the resource label. The resource label is part of the resource kind that determines whether the resources are treated as equivalent for the purpose of the balance check, i.e., of checking that the quantities of consumed and created resources match (see [Section 3.1](#) and

Section 3.2.2). The resource label must therefore be chosen carefully so that balance checks have the desired effect.

- Writing the resource logic function. Conceptually, this consists of anticipating all valid state transitions for the object and adding appropriate checks to guard them. It also involves parsing the resources in the action so that their values can be interpreted correctly in the logic checks.
- Assembling transaction schemas that touch multiple resources, ensuring that consumed and created resources are balanced, nonces are fresh, and compliance units are formed correctly.

This workflow is already error-prone for small applications, and its verbosity makes it unrealistic for large-scale application development. Furthermore, it demands an expert-level knowledge of the ARM.

2.2. How GOOSE helps

GOOSE introduces an object-oriented layer and a surface syntax that looks and feels like a conventional OOP language. For instance, a simple GOOSE program could look like this:

```
class Counter {
  var value: Nat

  constructor new(self: Counter) {
    self.value = 0
  }

  method increment(self: Counter; by: Nat) {
    self.value += by
  }
}

def myProgram() {
  c = Counter.new()
  c.increment(1)
  c.increment(2)
}
```

This code above defines the Counter class, with a private field called value that carries a natural number, a single constructor that initializes the value to zero, and a method that increments the counter by a given amount. Finally, it defines a program — independent of the class — that creates a counter object and increments it twice by different values. GOOSE compiles myProgram to an Anoma transaction, ready to be submitted to an Anoma controller.

2.2.1. Interface security

Apart from the familiar style of coding, GOOSE has another big advantage: interface security “for free”. In the above example, it is guaranteed that a Counter object can only be modified through its interface. For example, any transaction that attempts to decrement the value of a counter is rejected by the generated logic function, simply because no decrement method exists in the Counter class definition. Crucially, this remains true even for transactions crafted directly at the ARM level, without going through the GOOSE abstraction layer. In other words, there is effectively no way to circumvent the object’s interface.

Interface security means that only the operations specified in an object’s interface can be performed on the object, exactly as defined. The generated logic functions ensure that any operation on a resource representing an object matches one of the operations (methods, constructors, destructors, multi-methods) defined for the object’s class. The logic functions verify that the object is altered as specified by one of the operations, ensuring that all object fields are modified accordingly and that all nested calls are performed with the right arguments.

See [Section 5.5](#) for more details on how interface security is enforced by the GOOSE translation.

3. Anoma Resource Machine

In this section, we describe the Anoma Resource Machine (ARM) to the extent necessary to understand the details of the translation employed by GOOSE. The full specification of the ARM is available in [\[KG24\]](#). The version of the RM presented here is a simplification that omits some technical aspects not essential to GOOSE.

The ARM is the part of the Anoma protocol that defines and enforces the rules for valid state updates. Its role in the Anoma protocol is similar to the role of the Ethereum Virtual Machine in the Ethereum protocol. A major difference is the novel ARM resource transaction model, which is neither the account nor the UTXO model.

Two main concepts of the Anoma Resource Machine are resources and transactions.

3.1. Resources

A resource is an atomic unit of RM state. Resources are immutable: each can be created and consumed only once. The current RM state is determined by the resources which were created but not yet consumed.

A resource consists of the following.

- *logic*: Hash of the associated resource logic.

- *label*: Together with the resource logic, determines the kind of the resource.
- *quantity*: A natural number representing the quantity of the resource.
- *value*: Data associated with the resource.
- *ephemeral*: A boolean which determines whether the resource is ephemeral or persistent. Ephemeral resources are not stored in the RM state, and their existence is not checked when consumed.

The *resource kind* is determined by the resource label and logic. Resources of the same kind are treated as equivalent in the balance check, described later. Speaking informally, we typically identify the kind of a resource with its label, since resources with the same label typically have the same resource logic function.

The specification of the resource data structure above is simplified. In the ARM specification, resources also have fields for a *nonce* and a *nullifierKeyCommitment*.

Nonce is a number used only once – it guarantees resource uniqueness. There can only be one resource with a given nonce in RM state.

The nullifier key commitment corresponds to the nullifier key used to derive the resource nullifier. The *resource nullifier* is computed from the resource’s plaintext and the nullifier key. Publishing the resource nullifier by adding it to the nullifier set of RM state marks the resource as consumed [KG24].

The *nonce* and *nullifierKeyCommitment* fields are not essential for GOOSE, because we are only interested in properly using resource logics to encode valid object-state updates. In the GOOSE translation, only the *nonce* field plays a technical role in ensuring the uniqueness of object IDs.

3.1.1. Resource Logics

Each resource has an associated *resource logic* (RL) – an implementation of a pure boolean function that is evaluated when the resource is created or consumed. The RL of each consumed or created resource needs to evaluate to true for a transaction to be valid.

The RL of a resource *R* receives the following as input arguments:

- *self* – the resource *R* for which the logic is invoked,
- *isConsumed* – true if *self* is consumed in the action,
- *consumed* – list of resources consumed in the action,
- *created* – list of resources created in the action.

A resource logic is a pure mapping from its arguments to a boolean value. It does not have access to any external environment, ARM state (beyond what is provided in the arguments) or IO operations.

3.2. Transactions

A transaction specifies an RM state update. In particular, it specifies lists of consumed and created resources. Sums of quantities of consumed and created resources of the same kind must be equal for a transaction to be *balanced*.

3.2.1. Actions

A transaction is partitioned into actions. An action determines the scope for the resource logics of resources in the action.

For the purposes of GOOSE, the important aspect of an action is that it lists consumed and created resources. In the actual ARM for RISC Zero [BG⁺23], the structure of actions is more complex; they are divided into so-called compliance units, but these details are not essential to GOOSE, and we elide them here.

3.2.2. Balance check

In the current design of the resource machine, each resource is assigned a quantity. The quantity preservation principle states that quantity must be preserved, i.e., in a transaction, the sum of quantities of all consumed resources must equal the sum of quantities of the created resources of the same kind.

The balance check enforces the quantity preservation principle. Unbalanced transactions are not accepted by the ARM, and the state changes they specify cannot be performed.

The scope of the balance check is the whole transaction, not only a single action. A constituent action may be unbalanced, as long as the enveloping transaction is balanced.

For example, consider a transaction with a single action that contains the following resources.

consumed

- a resource of kind Dolphin with quantity 3
- a resource of kind Orange with quantity 2
- a resource of kind Orange with quantity 4

created

- a resource of kind Dolphin with quantity 1
- a resource of kind Dolphin with quantity 2

- a resource of kind Orange with quantity 3
- a resource of kind Orange with quantity 3

This transaction is balanced because the quantities of consumed and created resources with the same label and logic add up to the same number (3 for Dolphin, 6 for Orange). The transaction would be unbalanced, e.g., if we had only 1 consumed Dolphin instead of 3.

3.2.3. Examples

A transaction which creates a new persistent resource R contains a single action specified by:

consumed: R^e – ephemeral version of R , which is the same as R except that its *ephemeral* field is set to true.

created: R .

We need the ephemeral consumed resource for the transaction to be balanced. Ephemeral consumed resources are not checked for existence in the RM state. Persistent created resources are stored in the RM state once the transaction is accepted.

For the transaction to be valid, the RL of R needs to accept the action, i.e., it needs to evaluate to true with created and consumed resource arguments from the action. The RL could, for instance, forbid creating new resources except in certain circumstances.

Analogously, a transaction which destroys a persistent resource R contains a single action specified by:

consumed: R ,

created: R^e – ephemeral version of R , which is the same as R except that its *ephemeral* field is set to true.

We need the ephemeral created resource for the transaction to be balanced. Ephemeral created resources are not stored in the RM state. Persistent consumed resources are checked for existence in the RM state.

A transaction which modifies a single resource R , replacing it with R' , can be specified by a single action:

consumed: R ,

created: R' .

3.3. ARM Programs

ARM programs deal with the Resource Machine data structures (resources, transactions, etc.). ARM programs are a low-level compilation target for the GOOSE programs, which deal with higher-level GOOSE data structures — objects, methods, classes, etc.

An ARM program consists of a sequence of statements of the following form.

- *submitTransaction*: submit a transaction to an Anoma controller.
- *queryResource*: query a resource by ID from the ARM. This is an abstraction over the RM — we elide how or where resources are stored exactly.
- *rand*: generate a random number.

4. GOOSE Concepts

In this section, we provide a detailed description of the GOOSE application layer. We elaborate on the presentation of GOOSE concepts from [Section 2](#).

Two central concepts in GOOSE are *objects* and *messages*. Objects can send messages to each other, which represent calls to class members: constructors, destructors, and methods.

Object state is determined by the history of received messages. How an object responds to received messages depends on its object interface and its current state.

4.1. Objects

An *Object* consists of the following.

- *class*: Determines the class of the object, i.e., the type describing the object's interface (see [Section 4.3](#)),
- *id*: Globally unique ID of the object,
- *quantity*: Numeric object quantity. This field is treated specially because it is used in the balance check.
- *fields*: Fields of the object, storing object-specific values, e.g., the counter value for a counter object.

On the ARM level, objects are represented as resources such that:

- *class* is encoded in the *label* of the resource,
- *id* is encoded in the *value* field of the resource,
- *quantity* is mapped to the quantity field of the resource,

- private fields are stored in the *value* field of the resource.

The GOOSE-generated resource logics associated with object resources (object RLs) implement the business logic of all messages that an object can receive. The object RL looks for consumed message resources in the same action that it knows how to interpret as messages sent to the object. The object RL fails if it cannot interpret a message sent to the object, ensuring that the official object interface cannot be circumvented. In other words, only the operations defined in GOOSE for the object's class can be performed on the object, even if the transaction involving the object resource is created outside the GOOSE framework. This is a simple example of how interface security works (see [Section 5.5](#) for more details).

4.2. Messages

A *Message* is a data structure which represents a call to a class member (constructor, destructor, or method), a call to a multi-method, or an upgrade.

A message consists of the following.

- *id*: The message ID is a unique identifier which also specifies message type. A message can have one of the following types:
 - constructor, for object creation,
 - destructor, for object destruction,
 - method, for calling a method,
 - upgrade, for changing the object interface,
 - multi-method, for calling methods that involve several objects.
- *vals*: Message parameter values. The message parameters are object resources and randomly generated values used in the body of the call associated with the message. These must be included in the message because the associated RL cannot fetch object resources from the Anoma system or generate new object identifiers.
- *args*: The arguments of the call that the message represents. The type of the arguments depends on the message id. The message arguments are the non-self arguments of the corresponding member or multi-method call.
- *recipients*: The recipients of the message, i.e., the object IDs of the objects that the message is sent to.

- *signatures*: Authorization signatures for the message. Each signature consists of:
 - public identifier of the signer,
 - signature data: the message *id*, *args* and *vals* cryptographically signed with the signer’s private key.

In pseudocode, we write `msg.checkSignature(owner)` to denote a function call which checks whether the message `msg` has a signature signed by `owner`.

Messages are represented by ephemeral resources. The balance check is used to ensure that messages sent in one action are received in another action in the same transaction. More precisely, a sent message is represented by a created message resource which is in the same action as the resource that represents the sending object. A received message is represented by a consumed message resource which is in the same action as the resource that encodes the recipient object. See [Section 5.4](#) for more details.

4.3. Classes

A class is a user-defined data type that describes the structure (fields) and behaviour (methods) of objects.

In GOOSE, a class consists of the following.

- *name*: The name of the class, which, together with the version, uniquely identifies it.
- *version*: A numeric version of the class.
- *upgradeable*: A boolean which determines whether objects of the class can be upgraded to objects of a class with the same name but a higher version.
- *fields type*: The type of the private fields of objects in the class.
- *constructors*: A set of constructors.
- *destructors*: A set of destructors.
- *methods*: A set of methods.
- *invariant*: Extra class-specific logic. The class logic is the conjunction of the extra class logic and the member (constructor, destructor, method, multi-method) logics. The invariant is a boolean function with arguments:
 - *self*: the object for which the invariant is checked,

- resource logic arguments, as defined in [Section 3.1.1](#).

In the GOOSE pseudocode examples, we often omit some of the above, when empty or not important. In particular, it is not necessary for a class to define any constructors or destructors. In [Section 4.4](#) we present an example where a class with no constructors may be useful.

A class is a GOOSE-level concept with no direct counterpart in the ARM. Each object belongs to exactly one class which defines the types of its private fields and its behaviour. Calls to class members (constructors, destructors, methods) are identified with messages.

The RL associated with an object resource is determined by the object's class: the class implements the logics of the member calls (messages), as explained in [Section 4.1](#).

4.3.1. Class members

Class members include constructors, destructors, and methods.

A class member is defined by the following.

- *class*: The class of the created/destroyed/updated object.
- *Args*: The type of class member arguments.
- *body*: Member body, is a GOOSE program (see [Section 4.6](#)) parametrized by the *self* object (except for constructors) and arguments of type *Args*. The body program returns:
 - the object data of the created object in a constructor call,
 - nothing in a destructor call,
 - the updated *self* object in a method call.
- *invariant*: Extra member logic, i.e., constraints that must hold on each member call that the user specifies explicitly. These are combined with the member logic generated from the member body. The invariant is a boolean function with arguments:
 - *message*: the message corresponding to the member call,
 - *self*: the self object receiving the message (not present for a constructor call),
 - member arguments of type *Args*.

In the ARM, a member call is represented by an action containing the following, depending on the member type.

constructor

- a consumed message resource for the constructor message,
- a created persistent resource corresponding to the created object, and
- an ephemeral consumed resource to balance the created object resource.

destructor

- a consumed message resource for the destructor message,
- a consumed persistent resource corresponding to the destroyed *self* object, and
- an ephemeral created resource to balance the consumed object resource.

method

- one consumed message resource for the method message,
- one consumed persistent resource corresponding to the *self* object before the method call,
- one created persistent resource corresponding to the updated *self* object after the method call.

See also [Section 3.2.3](#). The RL of the member message checks if the action contains appropriate object resources, with the field values specified by the body of the member.

4.3.2. Example

Every class member has the *self* object as its first argument. The *self* is an object of the enclosing class.

The class member invariants are specified just after the member arguments with the syntax:

```
require(msg: Message) { <check> }
```

A member invariant has access to the same arguments as the corresponding member, plus the `msg` message argument.

We have not yet defined the GOOSE programs which make up the bodies of class members. In member bodies in [Example 1](#), we use some syntactic sugar that easily elaborates to GOOSE programs, as explained in [Section 4.6](#).

For the sake of readability, in our pseudocode examples, we take some liberties with how class members are presented. For example, in method definitions, the updated *self* object is not explicitly returned, but instead implicitly defined by imperative statements modifying the object's private fields. Analogously, in constructor definitions, the created object is implicitly defined by imperative assignments to the object fields.

Example 1.

```
class Counter {
  var value: Nat
  var owner: UserId

  constructor new(self: Counter; owner: UserId) {
    self.value = 0
    self.owner = owner
  }

  method increment(self: Counter; by: Nat)
  require(msg: Message) { msg.checkSignature(self.owner) }
  {
    self.value += by
  }
}

class TwoCounter {
  var count1: Counter
  var count2: Counter

  constructor new(self: TwoCounter; cnt1, cnt2: Counter) {
    self.count1 = cnt1
    self.count2 = cnt2
  }

  method incrementBoth(self: TwoCounter; n: Nat) {
    self.count1.increment(self.count2.value * n +
                          self.count1.value)
    self.count2.increment(self.count1.value * n +
                          self.count2.value)
  }
}
```

The `Counter` class represents an owned counter — only the owner of the counter is allowed to increment it.

The `TwoCounter` class has two fields `count1` and `count2` which store references to objects of type `Counter`. In all pseudocode we present, objects are always passed by reference. On the ARM level, object references are represented by object IDs. Accessing a field of an object (for example above in `self.count2.value` in `incrementBoth`) requires fetching the object data first. The translation from GOOSE programs to ARM programs inserts appropriate object fetches before accesses to object data.

4.4. Ecosystems and multi-methods

So far, the concepts we presented allow us to consume and create only one object resource at a time. A class method operates on a single *self* object that is modified by the method. A method can call other methods on other objects, but it cannot specify that, e.g., two objects be destroyed together, unless there is a method to destroy each object separately.

For a concrete example, consider the following `Bank` and `Check` classes.

```
class Bank {
  // current account balance for each user
  var accounts: Map UserId Nat

  constructor new(self: Bank) {
    self.accounts = Map.empty ()
  }
}

class Check {
  var owner: UserId
  var amout: Nat

  method transfer(self: Check; newOwner: UserId)
  require(msg: Message) { msg.checkSignature(self.owner) }
  {
    self.owner = newOwner
  }
}
```

We do not want to add a constructor to the `Check` class, because it should not be possible to create a check out of nothing. A check can only be created by a bank which needs to subtract the check amount from the account of the user issuing the check. Using the class methods presented so far, it is not possible to directly implement this functionality: a method for issuing a check would need to update the user's balance and create a check, but it cannot create a check if the `Check` class does not have any constructors (which we do not want to be available in general).

Multi-methods are a solution to this problem. In contrast to an ordinary class method, a multi-method operates on multiple *self* objects instead of

only one. It is possible to specify precisely which objects are destroyed, created, or updated.

An ecosystem is a scope for classes and multi-methods. Each class and multi-method belongs to a unique ecosystem. A multi-method operates on multiple self arguments — objects of classes in the ecosystem. The self arguments are consumed by the multi-method. There may be other arguments provided besides the *self* arguments.

An example multi-method for issuing a check follows.

```
method issueCheck(bank: Bank; owner: UserId, amount: Nat)
  require(msg: Message) {
    msg.checkSignature(owner)
    assert bank.accounts[owner].amount >= amount
  }
{
  bank.accounts[owner].amount -= amount
  create Check {owner = owner, amount = amount}
}
```

There is one *self* argument: *bank*. The corresponding bank object resource is consumed in the resulting transaction and an updated bank is created. The owner and amount arguments are additional non-self arguments.

The *issueCheck* multi-method needs to be defined in the same ecosystem as *Bank* and *Check*. The multi-method creates a new *Check* without exposing a *Check* constructor outside of the ecosystem.

4.5. Object upgrade

As mentioned in [Section 4.3](#), objects can be upgraded to objects with the same class and a higher version. For this to be allowed, the class of the object needs to be *upgradeable*. The upgrade mechanism is designed to enable future updates of objects to a newer version of their class. An arbitrary change to the object structure is allowed during the upgrade, provided the class name remains the same and the class version is higher.

On the level of the ARM, an upgrade is a special message resource with no arguments or parameters – it is used solely to enforce the upgrade logic. The message logic ensures that the created object resource has the same class as the consumed object resource but with a higher version.

4.6. GOOSE Programs

Having described all GOOSE concepts, we are ready to present *GOOSE Programs* more precisely. The pseudocode used for method bodies above is in fact syntactic sugar over GOOSE programs.

GOOSE programs provide an object-oriented abstraction over ARM programs to which they are translated. An GOOSE program consists of a list of statements of the following form.

- `objId = create Class.constructor args`. Call a constructor to create a new object.
- `destroy destructor objId args`. Call a destructor on an object with a given ID.
- `call method objId args`. Call a method of a self object with a given ID.
- `multiCall multiMethod objIds args`. Call a multi-method on self objects with given IDs.
- `upgrade objId to obj`. Upgrade an object with a given ID `objId` to an object `obj`. An upgrade is permitted only to an object of the same class with a newer version. The new object `obj` replaces the upgraded one. The object's ID is preserved.
- `obj = fetch objId`. Fetch an object with a given ID.
- `invoke fn args`. Invoke a function, i.e., a GOOSE subprogram.
- `return a`. Return a given value `a`.

GOOSE programs can also contain conditionals, matches and other control structures. We omit them here as they are not essential to the GOOSE translation.

4.6.1. Desugaring

The pseudocode used in the examples is a more readable representation of GOOSE programs. The desugaring of this representation to the actual GOOSE programs described above is relatively straightforward. We clarify it here in more detail.

- All objects are in fact object references represented by object IDs. For the sake of readability, we treat objects and object IDs interchangeably, leaving the `fetch` statements implicit. For example, referring to an object field `obj.count` requires fetching the object data first, so it is desugared to:

```
objData = fetch obj
objData.count
```

- In the pseudocode, we use imperative statements modifying the fields of a *self* object instead of returning the new *self* object at the end of a method or a constructor. This is easily desugared to appropriate return statements. For example, the method

```
method increment(self: Counter; n: Nat) {
  self.count += n
}
```

is desugared to

```
method increment(self: Counter; n: Nat) {
  selfObj = fetch self
  return {selfObj with count = selfObj.count + n}
}
```

- `obj = MyClass.constructor(args)` is desugared to:

```
obj = create MyClass.constructor args
```

When desugaring constructors, the *self* object is omitted from the arguments. Modifications to *self* in the body are replaced with returning the created object with appropriate field values.

- `obj.destructor(args)` is desugared to

```
destroy destructor obj args
```

- `obj.method(args)` is desugared to

```
call method obj args
```

- `multiMethod(obj1, ..., objN, args)` is desugared to

```
multiCall multiMethod obj1 .. objN args
```

- `fn(args)` is desugared to

```
invoke fn args
```

To illustrate the desugaring process, we present a desugared version of the example from [Section 4.3.2](#).

```
class Counter {
  var value: Nat
  var owner: UserId

  constructor new(owner: UserId) {
    return Counter {value = 0, owner = owner}
  }
}
```

```

method increment(self: Counter; by: Nat)
  require(msg: Message) {
    selfObj = fetch self
    invoke checkSignature msg selfObj.owner
  }
  {
    selfObj = fetch self
    return {selfObj with value = selfObj.value + by}
  }
}

class TwoCounter {
  var count1: Counter
  var count2: Counter

  constructor new(cnt1, cnt2: Counter) {
    return TwoCounter {count1 = cnt1, count2 = cnt2}
  }

  method incrementBoth(self: TwoCounter; n: Nat) {
    selfObj = fetch self
    count1Obj = fetch selfObj.count1
    count2Obj = fetch selfObj.count2
    call increment selfObj.count1
      (count2Obj.value * n + count1Obj.value)
    // We need to update count1Obj because it was just incremented
    count1Obj = fetch selfObj.count1
    call increment selfObj.count2
      (count2Obj.value * n + count1Obj.value)
  }
}

```

5. Translation

In this section, we describe the GOOSE translation in detail. The core part of the translation is from GOOSE Programs to ARM programs, which is divided into three main stages:

1. move all object fetches to the front of the program,
2. create a transaction corresponding to the part of the program following the fetches,
3. create resource logics for all resources involved in the transaction, based on the code of class member bodies and invariants.

We omit the desugaring described in the previous section and treat both versions of GOOSE programs interchangeably.

Before diving into details of how each GOOSE concept is represented in the ARM, we provide a general overview of the GOOSE translation.

5.1. Overview

In essence, the GOOSE translation can be understood as creating one action per received message corresponding to a class member or multi-method call. This action contains:

- consumed persistent object resources corresponding to *self* objects,
- created persistent object resources corresponding to updated *self* objects,
- consumed ephemeral message resource for the received message,
- created ephemeral message resources for the nested calls,
- consumed and created persistent object resources corresponding to the objects fetched in the body.

The translation from GOOSE programs to ARM programs can be summarized by the following phases.

1. Move all object fetches to the beginning of the program.
2. Parametrize the program by values of new object IDs that need to be generated for constructor calls.
3. For each class member or multi-method call, create an action implementing the manipulations on self objects in the body. For example, a method `increment` in class `Counter` defined by

```
method increment (n : Nat) {  
  self.count += n  
}
```

would result in an action with:

- one consumed object resource corresponding to *self*,
- one created object resource corresponding to *self* with the `count` field increased by `n`,
- one consumed message resource for `increment` containing the `n` argument,
- created message resources for all nested calls (none in this case),

- one consumed and one created object resource for each object fetched in the body (none in this case).
4. The previous points are applied recursively, resulting in a set of actions dependent on parameter values (fetched objects and generated object IDs).
 5. The object fetches and ID generation at the beginning of the program are translated to *queryResource* and *rand* ARM program commands.
 6. The actions are grouped into a single transaction, together with an action that sends the messages corresponding to the calls in the program. The *submitTransaction* command submits this transaction in the resulting ARM program.

The message logics check that the created object resources correspond to the modifications of consumed object resources specified by the bodies of corresponding class members or multi-methods, e.g., for methods the consumed *self* object resource is correctly updated into the created object resource.

The class logic checks that one of the following holds.

1. The *self* object is preserved (not modified).
2. There is exactly one consumed message resource, the *self* object is a recipient of the message and the message logic holds.

The class logic also checks the class invariant for *self*.

The resource logic of an object resource is the class logic for the class of the object. The resource logic of a message resource only checks if every recipient is present in the action when the message resource is consumed.

5.1.1. Example

As an example, consider the following GOOSE program `mutualIncrement`, analogous to the `incrementBoth` method of `TwoCounter` from [Section 4.3.2](#).

```
def mutualIncrement(cnt1, cnt2: Counter, n: Nat) {
  cnt1.increment(cnt2.value * n + cnt1.value)
  cnt2.increment(cnt1.value * n + cnt2.value)
}
```

After desugaring, this program becomes:

```
def mutualIncrement(cnt1, cnt2: Counter, n: Nat) {
  c1 = fetch cnt1
  c2 = fetch cnt2
  call increment cnt1 (c2.value * n + c1.value)
  c1 = fetch cnt1
  call increment cnt2 (c1.value * n + c2.value)
}
```

Moving object fetches to the front eliminates the fetch in the middle of the program in favour of updating `c1` according to the `Counter.increment` method.

```
def mutualIncrement(cnt1, cnt2: Counter, n: Nat) {
  c1 = fetch cnt1
  c2 = fetch cnt2
  call increment cnt1 (c2.value * n + c1.value)
  c1 = {c1 with value = c2.value * n + c1.value}
  call increment cnt2 (c1.value * n + c2.value)
}
```

This GOOSE program is translated into an ARM program performing the following.

1. `c1 = queryResource cnt1`
2. `c2 = queryResource cnt2`
3. `submitTransaction tx` where `tx` consists of two actions corresponding to the two calls and an action sending the call messages.

The objects `cnt1` and `cnt2` are represented by object IDs, so `c1.id` is `cnt1` and `c2.id` is `cnt2`.

Action for the first call:

- Consumed resources:
 - object resource for `c1`,
 - message resource for `increment` with recipient `cnt1` and argument `c1.value * n + c2.value`.
- Created resources:
 - object resource for:
$$c1' = \{c1 \text{ with value } := c1.value + c1.value * n + c2.value\}$$

Action for the second call:

- Consumed resources:
 - object resource for `c2`,
 - message resource for `increment` with recipient `cnt2` and argument `c2.value * n + c1'.value`.
- Created resources:

- object resource for:

$$c2' = \{c2 \text{ with value } := c2.\text{value} + c2.\text{value} * n + c1'.\text{value}\}$$

Action sending the call messages:

- Consumed resources: none.
- Created resources:
 - message resource for increment with recipient cnt1 and argument $c1.\text{value} * n + c2.\text{value}$.
 - message resource for increment with recipient cnt2 and argument $c2.\text{value} * n + c1'.\text{value}$.

In what follows, we describe in detail how each GOOSE concept is represented in the ARM and how GOOSE program statements are translated into ARM transactions.

5.2. Objects

Objects are translated to Resources. Every object is translated to a single resource, but it may contain references to sub-objects which are translated to separate resources. References to sub-objects are represented by object IDs. A sub-object is just an object reference, so the same object can be a sub-object of multiple parent objects.

Recall from [Section 4.1](#) that:

- *class* is stored in the *label* resource field,
- *id* is stored in the *value* field,
- *quantity* is stored in the *quantity* field,
- private fields are stored in the *value* field.

The resource logic of an object resource is determined by its class. This way, the resource kind (label & logic) determines the object class. The RL checks if the messages sent to the object correspond to class members or known multi-methods, and performs relevant message logic checks.

The ephemerality of the resource is not determined by the object. An object can map to either an ephemeral or a persistent resource depending on how it is used in the action. For example, in an action implementing an object constructor, there are two resources corresponding to the created object: a consumed ephemeral object resource and a created persistent object resource. See also [Section 3.2.3](#).

5.3. Tasks

To improve presentation clarity, we introduce *tasks*, an auxiliary data structure into which class members and multi-method calls are translated.

A *task* consists of the following.

- message. The message to be sent.
- actions. Task actions — ARM actions to perform parametrized by fetched objects and new object IDs. The actions component is a function which given task parameter values *params* (the fetched objects and object IDs the task depends on) returns the actions for the task.
- Params. Type of task parameters — objects to fetch from the Anoma system and new object IDs to generate. This component describes the *params* arguments of the actions function. For example, the parameter types

fetch ID1, genID, fetch ID2

indicate that *params* should consist of *obj1*, *newID*, *obj2* where *obj1*, *obj2* are objects fetched from Anoma with IDs ID1, ID2, respectively, and *newID* is a fresh object ID.

A task is translated into an ARM program that:

1. fetches the objects and generates object IDs specified by *Params*, and
2. submits a transaction with actions:
 - an action with one created resource corresponding to message, and
 - the task's actions instantiated with the fetched parameter values.

Tasks

<Params1, message1, actions1>, .., <ParamsN, messageN, actionsN>

can be composed with a new message *msg* and action *act*, parametrized by *Params0*, to create a task

<Params, message, actions>

such that:

- Params = Params0 ++ Params1 ++ .. ++ ParamsN,

- `message = msg,`
- `actions params0 params1 .. paramsN =`
`act params0 :: actions1 params1 ++ .. ++ actionsN paramsN.`

Above, the operation `::` denotes list cons and `++` denotes list concatenation. Typically, `act` in the last item above has among its created resources the message resources for `message1`, ..., `messageN`.

We translate class member and multi-method calls into tasks. Task composition is then used to combine the tasks arising from nested calls in the member body program with the action and the message generated for the call itself.

5.4. Messages and member calls

Messages are translated to ephemeral consumed resources (received messages) or ephemeral created resources (sent messages). All message data is stored in the resource label – this ensures that sent and received messages match, relying on the balance check in the Anoma Resource Machine.

The RL of a message resource checks that every recipient is present in the action when the message resource is consumed. The message logic (i.e. the logic implementing the constraints for the call associated with the message) is checked in the RL of the recipient object resource.

Calls to class members (constructor, destructor or method calls) and multi-methods are represented by message sending. These are translated into tasks – one task per interface call. The task is composed of sub-tasks generated for the nested calls in the body program of the class member or multi-method, a message corresponding to the called member, and an action sending the sub-task messages and implementing the changes to selves and the creation of objects specified by the member body.

5.4.1. Message logics

A message logic is a logic for a specific message (corresponding to a member call):

- constructor,
- destructor,
- method,
- multi-method,
- upgrade.

The message logics check the constraints for the corresponding member call, i.e., that the object resource in the action was modified correctly according to the member’s code.

The message logic is checked in the RL of the recipient object resource, not in the RL of the message resource. The RL of the message resource only checks that the required recipients are present.

5.4.2. Example

Recall from [Section 4.3.2](#) the Counter and TwoCounter classes with the methods increment and incrementBoth. We present it here in desugared form with fetches already moved to the front.

```
class Counter {
  var value: Nat
  var owner: UserId

  constructor new(owner: UserId) {
    return Counter {value = 0, owner = owner}
  }

  method increment(self: Counter; by: Nat)
  require(msg: Message) {
    selfObj = fetch self
    msg.checkSignature(selfObj.owner)
  }
  {
    selfObj = fetch self
    return {self with value = selfObj.value + by}
  }
}

class TwoCounter {
  var count1: Counter
  var count2: Counter

  constructor new(cnt1, cnt2: Counter) {
    return TwoCounter {count1 = cnt1, count2 = cnt2}
  }

  method incrementBoth(self: TwoCounter; n: Nat) {
    selfObj = fetch self
    c1 = fetch selfObj.count1
    c2 = fetch selfObj.count2
    selfObj.count1.increment(c2.value * n + c1.value)
    c1' = {c1 with value = c1.value + c2.value * n + c1.value}
    selfObj.count2.increment(c1'.value * n + c2.value)
  }
}
```

The task generated for a call to increment on self with argument n is:

- parameters: selfObj of type Counter (where selfObj is the fetched object with ID self),

- message: `increment(self, n)`,
- action:
 - consumed resources:
 - * object resource for `selfObj`,
 - * message resource for `increment(self, n)`,
 - created resources:
 - * object resource for
`{selfObj with value := selfObj.value + n}`

The message logic for `increment` checks if there is exactly one consumed object resource corresponding to an object `selfObj`, and exactly one created object resource corresponding to an object `selfObj'` such that

`selfObj' = {selfObj with value := selfObj.value + n}`.

The argument `n` is stored in the message resource. The message logic is invoked by the RL of the Counter object when a message resource for `increment` is present in the action.

The task generated for a call to `incrementBoth` on `self` with argument `n` composes the tasks for the two calls to `increment` with an action that sends the messages (has them as created resources) to the sub-objects and checks the constraints on the `selfObj` object of type `TwoCounter`.

- parameters: `selfObj` of type `TwoCounter`, `c1` and `c2` of type `Counter`,
- message: `incrementBoth(self, n)`
- actions:

1. action for the call to `increment` on `selfObj.count1`:

- consumed resources:
 - * object resource for `c1`,
 - * message resource for:
`increment(selfObj.count1,
c1.value * n + c2.value)`
- created resources:
 - * object resource for:

```
c1' = {c1 with
      value =
        c1.value +
        c2.value * n + c1.value}
```

2. action for the call to increment on selfObj.count2:

- consumed resources:
 - * object resource for c2,
 - * message resource for:
increment(selfObj.count2,
c2.value * n + c1'.value)
- created resources:
 - * object resource for:
c2' = {c2 with
value =
c2.value +
c2.value * n + c1'.value}

3. action for incrementBoth:

- consumed resources:
 - * object resource for selfObj,
 - * message resource for incrementBoth(self, n),
 - * object resources for c1 and c2,
- created resources:
 - * object resource for selfObj,
 - * message resources for
increment(selfObj.count1,
c1.value * n + c2.value)
and
increment(selfObj.count2,
c2.value * n + c1'.value)
 - * object resources for c1 and c2.

The message logic for incrementBoth checks if there is exactly one consumed object resource for selfObj, and exactly one created object resource for selfObj' = selfObj.

To ensure the consistency of sub-objects, we include the object resources for c1 and c2 in the consumed and created resources of the action for incrementBoth.

The message logic for `incrementBoth` checks that the object parameter values stored in the message resource correspond to the object resources for `c1` and `c2` present in the action, with their IDs equal to the IDs of objects fetched in the method body. If this check were not performed, a malicious user could prepare a transaction with arbitrary `Counter` objects in place of the `c1`, `c2` objects actually existing in the system. In other words, it needs to be checked that the object resources in the transaction actually correspond to the sub-objects of the `selfObj` object of class `TwoCounter`, i.e., to its `count1` and `count2` fields.

5.5. Interface security

The GOOSE translation ensures that the object interface cannot be circumvented. The class logic checks that the message sent to an object can be interpreted by it, and that the action correctly implements the message. It is not possible to modify an object resource in a way that does not correspond to sending a valid message. In this way, the GOOSE object interface defines permissible operations on the object.

Importantly, the object interface cannot be circumvented even if a malicious user tries to generate ARM transactions directly. The GOOSE object interface translates into constraints on object resources ensured by the resource logics. Below, we explain in more detail how RLs of object and message resources guarantee interface security.

- The class logic is invoked on object resource consumption in its RL. It checks that the class invariant holds, and either the object is not modified or its member logic evaluates to true. This ensures that the object is either not modified by the action, or it is modified in a way specified by one of the class-members or multi-methods.
- The member logic checks that the action contains exactly one consumed message resource for a message recognized by the recipient object. The message logic of this received message is then checked.
- The message logic checks the following.
 - The constraints on object resources in the action determined by the body of the class member or multi-method hold. This ensures that the action implements the body code, correctly updating the *self* objects.
 - The created message resources correspond to the messages sent in the body, with the right arguments computed from the body and message parameter values. This ensures the consistency of nested calls – that the calls specified in the body are actually

implemented by the action, i.e., the corresponding messages are sent with correct arguments.

- The action contains created and consumed resources corresponding to fetched objects provided in message parameter values. This ensures that the objects in the message parameter values actually exist in the system with the given data. The ARM will check the existence of persistent consumed object resources with given data and ID, and the message logic checks that these correspond to the objects stored in the message resource as parameter values. The check for created object resources with the same data ensures that the transaction is balanced and the fetched objects are not arbitrarily modified.
- The RL of the message resource checks — on consumption — that the object resource with the ID of the recipient object exists among the consumed resources in the action. This ensures that every message has a recipient in the action, and its logic cannot be ignored (the RL of the recipient object resource checks it).
- The balance check in the ARM ensures that in the transaction, every message resource for a sent message must have a matching message resource for a received message. This ensures that every message sent (message resource created) for a nested call in the action for the sending object has a corresponding received message (message resource consumed) in a different action for the recipient object.

5.6. Duality of GOOSE program code

A notable aspect of the translation is that the same body code is used to generate both the submitted transactions and the resource logics. The user can write ordinary object-oriented code without knowing or caring about how it maps to ARM concepts. This, however, may pose difficulties in implementing the GOOSE framework, because the ARM programs which submit the transactions and the resource logics need not even be written in the same programming language. The GOOSE approach may therefore require compiling the same object-oriented code to two or more fundamentally different targets. In the case of the Shielded Resource Machine, resource logics need to be compiled into zkVM bytecode, which imposes significant performance and functionality restrictions.

5.7. Class and member logics

Class logic is the logic associated with a class. It is the logic invoked by the RL when an object of this class is consumed. Member logic may be invoked

by a class logic to check that the *self* object is a recipient of the message and the associated message logic holds.

Class and member logics have access to RL arguments which contain the following.

- *selfRes*. The consumed resource corresponding to the *self* object of the class.
- *consumed*. List of resources consumed in the action.
- *created*. List of resources created in the action.

The *self* object is reconstructed from *selfRes*.

Class logic checks that the class invariant holds, and one of the following is true.

1. The *self* object is preserved (not modified) in the action, i.e., *selfRes* is persistent, there is exactly one persistent created resource *selfRes'* with the ID *self.id* and *selfRes'* corresponds to *self* (i.e., *selfRes* and *selfRes'* represent the same object with equal fields).
2. The member logic holds for *self*, i.e., the *self* object is a recipient of the message and the message logic holds. More precisely:
 - *consumed* contains exactly one message resource for a message *msg* in the ecosystem of the class,
 - *self.id* is in *msg.recipients*,
 - The message logic for *msg* holds.

5.8. Constructor

5.8.1. Constructor call

Constructor calls are translated to tasks. The task for a call to a constructor *constr* with arguments *args* is the composition of the tasks for nested calls in the constructor body with the constructor action specified by the following. See also [Section 3.2.3](#).

- Consumed resources:
 - one ephemeral object resource corresponding to the created object, i.e., the object returned by the constructor body,
 - one ephemeral message resource for the received constructor message, with message arguments set to *args*,

- persistent object resources corresponding to the objects fetched in the constructor body.
- Created resources:
 - one persistent object resource corresponding to the created object,
 - ephemeral message resources for all messages sent in the constructor body (corresponding to nested calls),
 - persistent object resources corresponding to the objects fetched in the constructor body.

The randomly generated IDs of created objects are ensured to be unique by making them equal to the nonce of the consumed ephemeral object resource.

5.8.2. Constructor message logic

Constructor message logic is the logic associated with the constructor message. The message logic is checked in the RL of the recipient object resource on consumption. For a constructor message, the recipient object resource is the ephemeral consumed resource corresponding to the created object.

Constructor message logic has access to RL arguments which contain the following.

- msgRes. The resource of the constructor message.
- consumed. List of resources consumed in the action.
- created. List of resources created in the action.

Constructor message logic for a constructor constr performs the following checks.

- consumed contains:
 - one ephemeral object resource corresponding to the created object,
 - persistent object resources corresponding to the objects fetched in the constructor body.
- created contains:
 - one persistent object resource corresponding to the created object,

- ephemeral message resources for all messages sent in the constructor body, with arguments matching the arguments to the nested calls,
 - persistent object resources corresponding to the objects fetched in the constructor body.
- consumed and created may contain more message resources, but not any object resources other than the ones specified above.
 - The invariant of the constructor holds.

5.9. Destructor

5.9.1. Destructor call

Destructor calls are translated to tasks. The task for a call to a destructor `destr` on `self` with arguments `args` is the composition of the tasks for nested calls in the destructor body, with the destructor action specified by the following. See also [Section 3.2.3](#).

- Consumed resources:
 - one persistent object resource corresponding to `self`,
 - one ephemeral message resource for the received destructor message, with message arguments set to `args`,
 - persistent object resources corresponding to the objects fetched in the destructor body.
- Created resources:
 - one ephemeral object resource corresponding to `self`,
 - ephemeral message resources for all messages sent in the destructor body (corresponding to nested calls),
 - persistent object resources corresponding to the objects fetched in the destructor body.

5.9.2. Destructor message logic

Destructor message logic is the logic associated with the destructor message. Destructor message logic has access to the following RL arguments.

- `msgRes`. The resource of the destructor message.

- consumed. List of resources consumed in the action.
- created. List of resources created in the action.

Destructor message logic for a destructor `destr` performs the following checks.

- consumed contains:
 - one persistent object resource `selfRes` corresponding to the `self` object,
 - persistent object resources corresponding to the objects fetched in the destructor body (matching the parameter values stored in the message).
- created contains:
 - one ephemeral object resource `selfRes'` corresponding to the `self` object,
 - ephemeral message resources for all messages sent in the destructor body, with arguments matching those of nested calls,
 - persistent object resources corresponding to the objects fetched in the destructor body (matching the parameter values stored in the message).
- consumed and created may contain more message resources, but not additional object resources.
- The invariant of the destructor holds.

5.10. Method

5.10.1. Method call

Method calls are translated to tasks. The task for a call to a method `method` on `self` with arguments `args` is the composition of the tasks for nested calls in the method body with the method action specified by the following. See also [Section 3.2.3](#).

- Consumed resources:
 - one persistent object resource for `self`,
 - one ephemeral message resource for the received method message, with message arguments set to `args`,

- persistent object resources corresponding to the objects fetched in the method body.
- Created resources:
 - one persistent object resource corresponding to the updated *self* object, i.e., the updated object returned in the desugared method body (see [Section 4.6.1](#)),
 - ephemeral message resources for all messages sent in the method body,
 - persistent object resources corresponding to the objects fetched in the method body.

5.10.2. Method message logic

Method message logic has access to the following arguments.

- `msgRes`. The resource for the method message.
- `consumed`. List of resources consumed in the action.
- `created`. List of resources created in the action.

Method message logic performs the following checks.

- `consumed` contains:
 - one persistent object resource `selfRes` for `self`,
 - persistent object resources fetched in the method body.
- `created` contains:
 - one persistent object resource `selfRes'` corresponding to the updated `self` object,
 - ephemeral message resources for all messages sent in the method body,
 - persistent object resources fetched in the method body (matching the parameter values stored in the message).
- No other object resources appear in `consumed` or `created`.
- The method invariant holds.

5.11. Upgrade

5.11.1. Upgrade call

Upgrade calls are translated into tasks. The task for an upgrade of *self* to *obj* consists of the following.

- Consumed resources:
 - one persistent object resource for *self*,
 - one ephemeral message resource for the received upgrade message.
- Created resources:
 - one persistent object resource corresponding to *obj*.

5.11.2. Upgrade message logic

Upgrade message logic has access to the following arguments.

- *consumed*. List of resources consumed in the action.
- *created*. List of resources created in the action.

Upgrade message logic performs the following checks.

- *consumed* contains exactly one persistent object resource *selfRes* corresponding to the *self* object.
- *created* contains exactly one persistent object resource *objRes* corresponding to the *obj* upgraded object.
- *obj.id = self.id* holds and the class of *obj* is the class of *self* with higher version.
- *consumed* and *created* may contain additional message resources, but no other object resources.

5.12. Multi-method

5.12.1. Multi-method call

Multi-method calls are translated into tasks. The task for calling multi-method `multiMethod` on a list *selfes* of *self* objects with additional arguments *args* is the composition of the tasks for nested calls with the action defined by the following.

- Consumed resources:

- persistent object resources for selves,
 - ephemeral object resources for constructed objects,
 - one ephemeral message resource for the multi-method message,
 - persistent object resources fetched in the body.
- Created resources:
 - persistent object resources for assembled objects,
 - ephemeral object resources for destroyed objects,
 - persistent object resources for constructed objects,
 - ephemeral message resources for nested calls,
 - persistent object resources fetched in the body.

5.12.2. Multi-method message logic

Multi-method message logic has access to RL arguments which contain the following.

- `msgRes`. The resource of the method message `msg`, which contains the method call arguments `args` and parameter values `vals`.
- `consumed`. List of resources consumed in the action.
- `created`. List of resources created in the action.

Given the number `n` of selves, we reconstruct the *self* objects from the first `n` resources in `consumed`, compute the multi-method result, and partition resources into the following lists.

- `disassembled`. List of persistent object resources corresponding to initial values of the *self* objects that are updated in the multi-method body.
- `destroyed`. List of persistent object resources corresponding to the *self* objects that are destroyed in the multi-method body.
- `constructedEph`. List of ephemeral object resources corresponding to the objects created in the multi-method body.
- `fetchedConsumed`. List of persistent object resources corresponding to the objects fetched in the multi-method body.

Similarly, the `created` list is partitioned into the following.

- assembled. List of persistent object resources corresponding to final values of the *self* objects that are updated in the multi-method body.
- destroyedEph. List of ephemeral object resources corresponding to the *self* objects that are destroyed in the multi-method body.
- constructed. List of persistent object resources corresponding to the objects created in the multi-method body.
- fetchedCreated. List of persistent object resources corresponding to the objects fetched in the multi-method body.

Multi-method message logic performs the following checks.

- The disassembled, assembled, destroyed, and constructed (persistent and ephemeral) resources correspond to the respective objects.
- Resources in each partition have correct persistence/ephemerality,
- Fetched resources (fetchedConsumed and fetchedCreated) match the objects fetched in the multi-method body provided in the parameter values *vals* stored in the message.
- The multi-method invariant holds.

6. Extended example: Kudos Bank

In this section, we present an extended example of the Kudos Bank application implemented in GOOSE. The example is intended to show the full capabilities of GOOSE. We use pseudocode syntax consistent with GOOSE pseudocode from earlier sections.

Kudos bank application supports the following operations:

- open and close a bank;
- create tokens of their own denomination and store them in some bank;
- transfer owned tokens to another user within the same bank;
- issue, transfer, and deposit checks;
- run an auction.

6.1. Opening a bank

Any user can create a new bank, which they will own. A bank is an object that keeps track of the balances of its clients. Concretely, a bank consists of a map from public id (the client) to their account. An account maps each denomination to a quantity. A denomination is a public key, which identifies the originator of that denomination.

```

synonym Denom = PubId

synonym Account = Map Denom Nat

class Bank {
  var balances: Map PubId Account
  var owner: PubId

  constructor new(newOwner: PubId) {
    balances = emptyMap()
    owner = newOwner
  }

  method mint(self : Bank; originator: PubId, n: Nat) {
    require(msg: Message) {
      msg.checkSignature originator
      assert n > 0
    }
    self.balances[originator][originator] += n
  }
}

```

6.2. Minting

A user can only mint tokens of their denomination.

The mint method shown below has two parts, the body and the invariant. In the body, we increment the originator's balance by n tokens of their denomination. In the invariant, we include security checks. In particular, we check that the originator has authorized with his signature the invocation of the method, in this case, minting kudos.

```

class Bank {
  ...

  method mint(self : Bank; originator: PubId, n: Nat) {
    require(msg : Message) {
      msg.checkSignature originator
      assert n > 0
    }
    self.balances[originator][originator] += n
  }
}

```

6.3. Internal kudos transfers

A user can transfer any amount of tokens that they own to another user within the same bank. In the body of the method, we adjust the balances of the sender and the receiver to reflect the transfer. In the invariant, we check

that the sender authorized the transfer. Note that this only allows transfers to happen within a bank.

```
class Bank {
  ...

  method transfer(self : Bank;
    owner: PubId, n: Nat, newOwner: PubId, denom: Denomination) {
    require(msg: Message) {
      msg.checkSignature owner
      assert n <= self.balances[owner][denom]
      assert n > 0
    }
    self.balances[owner][denom] -= n
    self.balances[newOwner][denom] += n
  }
}
```

6.4. Check notes

A bank check is a self-contained proof that someone owns a certain amount of a token, in a specific denomination. A check can be issued by a bank, transferred to someone else—independently of any bank—and deposited back into a bank.

The method for transferring a check can be defined analogously to a bank transfer. Issuing or depositing a check, however, requires interacting with multiple objects—for example, issuing a check updates both the bank’s balances and creates a new Check object. In GOOSE, this can be achieved by defining an ecosystem that contains the two classes Bank and Check, and then adding the multi-methods `issueCheck` and `depositCheck` to that ecosystem.

```
ecosystem KudosBank {
  class Bank {
    ...
  }

  class Check {
    var owner: PubId
    var quantity: Nat
    var denom: Denom

    method transfer(self : Check; newOwner: PubId) {
      require(msg: Message) {
        msg.checkSignature self.owner
      }
      self.owner := newOwner
    }
  }
}
```

```

method issueCheck(bank: Bank; owner: PubId, n: Nat, d: Denom) {
  require(msg: Message) {
    msg.checkSignature owner
    assert n <= self.balances[owner][d]
    assert n > 0
  }
  bank.balances[owner][d] -= n
  create Check {
    owner = owner,
    quantity = n,
    denom = d
  }
}

method depositCheck(bank: Bank, check: Check) {
  require(msg: Message) {
    msg.checkSignature check.owner
  }
  bank.balances[check.owner][check.denom] += check.quantity
  destroy check
}
}

```

6.5. Auction

An auction is run to exchange a certain amount of tokens you own for the highest bid in a desired denomination. An auction has three stages.

1. A user opens an auction to sell n tokens they own of denomination x in exchange for tokens of denomination y . The auction specifies the desired denomination y .
2. Any user can place a bid. Placing a bid means committing some amount of tokens of denomination y to the auction. Each new bid must exceed the current highest bid. When a bid is trumped, the owner of the previous highest bid gets their tokens back.
3. The auction owner closes the auction and the final transaction takes place: the highest bidder receives n tokens of denomination x , and the auction owner receives m tokens of denomination y , where m is the maximum bid.

```

ecosystem KudosBank {
  ...

  class Auction {
    var owner: PubKey
  }
}

```

```

var auctionedDenomination: Denom
var auctionedQuantity: Nat
var biddingDenomination: Denom
var highestBid: Nat
var highestBidder: PubKey
}

method newAuction(check: Check; desired: Denom) {
  require(msg : Message) {
    msg.checkSignature check.owner
  }
  create Auction {
    owner = check.owner,
    auctionedDenomination = check.denom,
    auctionedQuantity = check.quantity,
    biddingDenomination = desired,
    highestBid = 0,
    highestBidder = check.owner
  }
  destroy check
}

method bid(check: Check, auction: Auction) {
  require(msg: Message) {
    msg.checkSignature check.owner
    assert check.quantity > auction.highestBid
  }
  create Check {
    owner = auction.highestBidder,
    quantity = auction.highestBid,
    denomination = auction.biddingDenomination
  }
  auction.highestBidder = check.owner
  auction.highestBid = check.quantity
  destroy check
}

method end(auction: Auction) {
  require(msg: Message) {
    msg.checkSignature auction.owner
  }
  create Check {
    owner = auction.highestBidder,
    quantity = auction.auctionedQuantity,
    denomination = auction.auctionedDenomination
  }
  create Check {
    owner = auction.owner,
    quantity = auction.highestBid,
    denomination = auction.biddingDenomination
  }
}

```

```
    }  
    destroy auction  
  }  
}
```

7. Conclusion

GOOSE provides an object-oriented abstraction layer on top of the Anoma Resource Machine that enables application development using classes, objects, and methods, without any knowledge of the ARM. At the conceptual level, GOOSE identifies objects with RM resources, and calls to methods, constructors, destructors, upgrades, and multi-methods with messages that induce actions within a transaction. This view allows application logic to be written in a familiar programming style while the compiler produces transactions and resource logics that are correct by construction.

A central contribution of GOOSE is the precise account of how high-level object-oriented constructs are represented in the ARM. We described how objects, messages, and classes translate to resources and resource logics, and how this mapping is organized via the intermediate notion of tasks. The translation pipeline from GOOSE programs to ARM programs first hoists object fetches, then constructs a single transaction as a composition of per-message tasks, and finally generates resource logics that securely encode the intended object behaviour.

The GOOSE framework delivers strong interface security guarantees (see [Section 5.5](#)). For each object, its class and member definitions induce a resource logic that enforces the object’s interface at the RM level. Any valid transaction that modifies an object must correspond to a sequence of recognized messages whose message logics and class invariants hold. Importantly, this holds regardless of whether the transaction was produced by a GOOSE compiler or handcrafted directly for the RM. In this way, GOOSE offers an abstraction that is not merely a programming convenience but also comes with security guarantees.

The GOOSE translation process is compositional: each class member or multi-method call is compiled independently to a task. The tasks for calls in a GOOSE program are composed into a single transaction. This modularity scales to complex patterns of interaction, as illustrated by the Kudos Bank example, which combines ordinary methods and multi-methods to support minting, transfers, check issuance and auctions. The same member bodies serve a dual role (see [Section 5.6](#)): they define the state updates implemented by transactions and simultaneously specify the constraints of the resource logics that validate those updates.

In summary, GOOSE provides an object-oriented layer over the ARM that

maps objects and messages to resources and resource logics through a compositional translation pipeline. By generating resource logics that enforce class interfaces and invariant checks, GOOSE ensures that any valid state change, compiled or handwritten, respects intended object behavior.

8. Acknowledgements

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References

- BG⁺23. Jeremy Bruestle, Paul Gafni, et al. RISC Zero zkVM: scalable, transparent arguments of RISC-V integrity. *Draft*. July, 29, 2023. (cit. on p. 9.)
- CMR25. Lukasz Czajka and Jan Mas Rovira. GOOSE in Lean 4. *Anoma Research Topics*, Dec 2025. doi:10.5281/zenodo.17983479. (cit. on p. 46.)
- GYB23. Christopher Goes, Awa Sun Yin, and Adrian Brink. Anoma: a unified architecture for full-stack decentralised applications. *Anoma Research Topics*, Aug 2023. URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8279841>, doi:10.5281/zenodo.8279842. (cit. on p. 3.)
- Hei25. Tobias Heindel. Anoma Virtual Machine. *Anoma Research Topics*, Dec 2025. (cit. on p. 4.)
- HR24. Michael Heuer and D Reusche. Intent-centric Applications for the Anoma Resource Machine. *Anoma Research Topics*, Aug 2024. URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13340447>, doi:10.5281/zenodo.13340448. (cit. on p. 5.)
- KG24. Yulia Khalniyazova and Christopher Goes. Anoma Resource Machine Specification. *Anoma Research Topics*, Jun 2024. URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10498990>, doi:10.5281/zenodo.10689620. (cit. on pp. 3, 5, 7, and 8.)
- MU21. Leonardo de Moura and Sebastian Ullrich. The Lean 4 theorem prover and programming language. In *International Conference on Automated Deduction*, pages 625–635. Springer, 2021. (cit. on p. 46.)

A. Implementation of GOOSE in Lean 4

We implemented a prototype of GOOSE [CMR25] in Lean 4 [MU21]. The GOOSE prototype provides a translation from GOOSE object structures to Anoma Resource Machine structures, both represented in Lean 4. The implemented translation follows closely the description in the present report. The GOOSE prototype in Lean 4 is available at <https://github.com/anoma/goose-lean>.

Throughout this document, we have presented code snippets using a pseudocode syntax similar to mainstream object-oriented imperative programming languages. This choice was made to prioritize readability and familiarity for a broader audience. It is important to note that we have not implemented either a parser or a translation mechanism for the internal representation of GOOSE from this ideal syntax. Consequently, the examples implemented in the Lean project have been written directly using the internal representation.

The purpose of this section is to explicitly describe the correspondence between the presented syntax and the internal representation. We believe that this correspondence is intuitive and self-explanatory, but we include it here for completeness. To make this concrete, we will revisit the Kudos Bank example, focusing specifically on the syntax.

Throughout this section, we will use these color codes:

- **GOOSE**: Represents the pseudocode syntax we have used throughout this document.
- **GOOSE IR**: Represents the Lean code in which our examples have been implemented. This would be the target compilation language of the **GOOSE** syntax.
- **Lean Reference**: Used to show code fragments of the Lean implementation.

A.1. Classes

The basic definition of the Bank class implemented in pseudocode.

```
GOOSE
synonym Denom = PubId
synonym Account = Map Denom Nat

class Bank {
  var balances: Map PubId Account
  var owner: PubId

  ...
}
```

In Lean, we can define a structure with the corresponding fields.

GOOSE IR (Lean)

```
def Denom := PubId
def Account := Map Denom Nat

structure KudosBank where
  owner : PubId
  balances : Map PubId Account
```

A core design choice of GOOSE is that the language of the GOOSE programs is embedded in the host language. This allows us to reuse all the language features of the host language, Lean. In practice, this means that when we write GOOSE programs, we can make use of Lean's structures, inductive types, match expressions, let statements, and so on.

Adding a method requires introducing a *class label*. Intuitively, a class label is the interface of the class: it contains the types of its fields and the signatures of its constructors, methods, and destructors; but not the implementation. One could think of as an analogous to the headers file for C.

Lean, Reference

```
structure Label where
  name : String
  PrivateFields : SomeType
  ...
```

The relevant part of the class label would be defined thus:

GOOSE IR (Lean)

```
def BankLabel : Class.Label where
  name := "KudosBank"
  PrivateFields := <KudosBank>
  ...
```

We can now extend the class to add the new constructor.

GOOSE

```
constructor new(newOwner: PubId) {
  balances = emptyMap()
  owner = newOwner
}
```

In the class label definition we add `ConstructorId` and a function that

maps each constructor id to the type of its arguments:

Lean, Reference

```
structure Label where
  ...
  ConstructorId : Type
  ConstructorArgs : ConstructorId -> SomeType
```

For our example, adding a constructor entails defining an enum type for the identifiers of the constructors and the function for the type of the arguments:

GOOSE IR (Lean)

```
inductive Constructors where
  | Open : Constructors

def BankLabel : Class.Label where
  ...
  ConstructorId := Constructors

  ConstructorArgs := fun
  | Constructors.Open => <PubId>
```

In order to add add methods and destructors to the label, an analogous change is required. We skip ahead to avoid unnecessary repetition.

Let us proceed by showing how to implement a class method. We will use transfer as an example.

GOOSE

```
class Bank {
  ...

  method transfer(self : Bank;
    owner: PubId, n: Nat, newOwner: PubId, denom: Denomination) {
    require(msg: Message) {
      msg.checkSignature owner
      assert n <= self.balances[owner][denom]
      assert n > 0
    }
    self.balances[owner][denom] -= n
    self.balances[newOwner][denom] += n
  }
}
```

In the internal representation we define the body and the require section separately. In the actual codebase we named the require argument invariant, but we have renamed it here for consistency with the pseudocode syntax.

GOOSE IR (Lean)

```
def kudosTransfer : Method label Classes.Bank Methods.Transfer :=
defMethod KudosBank
  (body := fun (self : KudosBank) (args : TransferArgs) =>
    return self.overBalances (fun b => b
      |> Balances.addTokens args.newOwner args.denom args.quantity
      |> Balances.subTokens args.oldOwner args.denom args.quantity)
  )
  (require := fun (msg : Message label) (self : KudosBank) (args :
    TransferArgs) =>
    0 < args.quantity
    && msg.checkSignature args.oldOwner
    && args.quantity <= self.getBalance args.oldOwner args.denom)
```

A.2. Ecosystems

Like classes, ecosystems also have a label associated with them. In this label we specify which classes belong to it and what are the type signatures of its multi-methods.

To specify the classes in the ecosystem, we specify an enum type and a function that maps each of the constructors to a class label.

Lean, Reference

```
structure Ecosystem.Label where
  ...
  ClassId : Type
  classLabel : ClassId → Class.Label
```

Specifying the type signatures of the multi-methods is done via these fields:

Lean, Reference

```
structure Ecosystem.Label where
  ...
  MultiMethodId : Type
  MultiMethodArgs : MultiMethodId → SomeType
  MultiMethodObjectArgNames : MultiMethodId → Type
  MultiMethodObjectArgClass :
    {f : MultiMethodId} → MultiMethodObjectArgNames f → ClassId
```

The fields above contain the following information:

- `MultiMethodId` contains an enum type that enumerates all the multi-method ids.
- `MultiMethodArgs` maps each multi-method id to the type of its non-object arguments.
- `MultiMethodObjectArgNames` maps each multi-method id an enum type that has a constructor for each object argument. Each one of these constructors represents an argument name.
- `MultiMethodObjectArgClass` maps each argument name to an object class id.

Let us make it concrete by using the `issueCheck` multi-method as an example. To facilitate readability we copy the code below.

GOOSE

```
method issueCheck(bank: Bank; owner: UserId, amount: Nat)
  require(msg: Message) {
    msg.checkSignature(owner) &&
    bank.accounts[owner].amount >= amount
  }
{
  bank.accounts[owner].amount -= amount
  create Check {owner = owner, amount = amount}
}
```

In the arguments section we first specify the object arguments and then the rest. They two categories are separated by a semicolon. In this case we have a single object argument, so we would have:

GOOSE IR (Lean)

```
inductive IssueCheck.ClassArgNames where
  | bank

def label : AVM.Ecosystem.Label where
  ...
MultiMethodObjectArgNames := fun
  | .IssueCheck => IssueCheck.ClassArgNames
```

For the non-object arguments:

GOOSE IR (Lean)

```
structure IssueCheck.Args where
  denomination : Denomination
  owner : PublicKey
  quantity : Nat

def label : AVM.Ecosystem.Label where
  ...
MultiMethodArgs := fun
  | .IssueCheck => IssueCheck.Args
```

Then, to implement the `issueCheck` multi-method we use the `defMultiMethod` helper function. The important arguments are:

- `argsInfo`: The relevant instances for the object arguments.
- `require`: A boolean precondition that must be satisfied. Equivalent to

the require argument in the class method.

- body: The actual implementation of the multi-method.

The arguments `argsInfo` and `require` can be provided straightforwardly:

GOOSE IR (Lean)

```
def issueCheck : @Ecosystem.MultiMethod label .IssueCheck :=
  defMultiMethod label MultiMethods.IssueCheck
  (argsInfo := fun
    | .bank =>
      { type := KudosBank, isObjectOf := KudosBank.instIsObjectOf })
  (require := fun msg selves args =>
    let bank := selves .bank
    msg.checkSignature args.owner
    && 0 < args.quantity
    && args.quantity <= bank.getBalance args.owner args.denomination)
  (body := ...)
```

In order to explain the body argument we first need to understand the return type of a multi-method and some related types:

Lean, Reference

```
structure MultiMethodResult {lab : Ecosystem.Label}
  (multiId : lab.MultiMethodId) where
  argDeconstruction :
    multiId.ObjectArgNames → AVM.DeconstructionKind
  assembled : Assembled argDeconstruction
  constructed : List AnObject

inductive DeconstructionKind where
  | Destroyed
  | Disassembled

structure Assembled
  {label : Ecosystem.Label}
  {multiId : label.MultiMethodId}
  (argDeconstruction : multiId.ObjectArgNames → DeconstructionKind)
  where
  withOldUid : (arg : multiId.ObjectArgNames)
    → argDeconstruction arg = .Disassembled
    → Option (ObjectData arg.classId)
  withNewUid : List SomeObjectData
```

The fields in `MultiMethodResult` mean the following:

- `argDeconstruction`: For each object argument we specify how it should be deconstructed. There are two options; if it is destroyed, an ephemeral resource is automatically inserted to satisfy the balance constraint. If it is disassembled, the object is meant to be balanced by one or more created objects. The most common case for disassembly is to update the data in an object.
- `assembled`: Contains the created objects. The `withOldUid` defines the subset of the dissembled objects that should preserve their original object id. The objects in the `withNewUid` list will be assigned fresh ids.
- `constructed`: A list of objects to be created with fresh ids. Additionally, ephemeral consumed objects will be added to balance the transaction.

Finally, we can provide the body argument. In our example, we update the balances in the bank, which preserves the object id. Also, a new check object is constructed.

GOOSE IR (Lean)

```
def issueCheck : @Ecosystem.MultiMethod label .IssueCheck :=
defMultiMethod label MultiMethods.IssueCheck
(argsInfo := ...)
(require := ...)
(body := fun selves args =>
  return
  { assembled := {
    withOldUid arg _ :=
      match arg with
      | .bank =>
        let bank' :=
          (selves .bank).overBalances
          (fun b => b
            |> Balances.subTokens args.owner args.denomination
            args.quantity)
        some { obj := bank', isObjectOf := KudosBank.instIsObjectOf }
    withNewUid := [] }
  argDeconstruction := fun
  | .bank => .Disassembled
  constructed := [{ denomination := args.denomination
    owner := args.owner
    quantity := args.quantity
    : Check }])
```